
LEGAL AND FINANCIAL ASPECTS OF VOYAGE CHARTER UNDER ENGLISH PRIVATE MARITIME LAW

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Abstract

This article examines the legal and financial structure of the **voyage charter** under **English private maritime law**, highlighting its significance within the framework of tramp shipping. It discusses the operational and legal responsibilities of the shipowner and charterer, the division of costs and liabilities, and the implications of Free In and Out freight terms. The analysis includes the interaction between different types of charter arrangements—bareboat, time, and voyage—and their effect on contractual obligations and cargo liability, especially within charter chains. Attention is given to the formal and substantive elements of voyage charterparties, such as the description of the vessel, voyage, cargo, and freight determination. Through references to case law and academic doctrine, the article situates the voyage charter in both historical and contemporary contexts of commercial maritime practice.

Keywords: voyage charter, English maritime law, charterparty, freight terms, tramp shipping, shipowner liability, chain of charters, contract of affreightment, cargo operations

1. Introduction

Voyage charters represent a fundamental legal and commercial instrument in maritime trade, particularly under English private maritime law. These charters govern the carriage of cargo between ports and typically involve a single charterer and one or more vessels. When covering multiple shipments over an extended period, the relationship may take the form of a Contract of Affreightment (COA) or a Volume Contract.

(Cooke et al., 2014, para. 1.2). Voyage charters for more than one voyage may fall into a number of different categories. They may be 'consecutive voyage charters,' where each voyage follows on directly from the previous one; they may be 'intermittent voyage charters,' or they may be so-called 'contracts of affreightment' or 'tonnage contracts' for a series of periodic voyages in a vessel or vessels to be nominated thereafter. All are often referred to merely as 'COAs' to highlight their characteristics. It is common for single-voyage charter forms to be adapted to cover multiple-voyage contracts, and this can lead to difficulties concerning, for example, cancellation, liens, and the effect of the Hague Rules when incorporated, not to mention the identification of the relevant parties. [1]

(HandyBulk, n.d.): A Voyage or Spot Charter refers to a situation where a ship is contracted for a single Voyage between designated Ports. This type of charter is widely used in Bulk/Tramp Trading (Chartering Market) but is nearly absent in the Liner Shipping Market, where Liner Carriers handle scheduled Voyages using either their own ships or those chartered on a period basis from individual Shipowners." [2]

(Li and Yang, 2024) observe that voyage charterparties are effectively used in inland tramp shipping, as they offer the flexibility needed to align with the unique operational conditions of inland navigation. [3]

Under a voyage charter, the shipowner retains both technical and commercial management of the vessel, while the charterer is responsible for arranging cargo operations. The vessel may previously have been subject to a bareboat and/or time charter, creating a chain of charter parties. In a bareboat charter, although legal ownership of the vessel remains with the registered shipowner, possession and full control of the vessel are transferred to the bareboat charterer, who becomes the de facto ship operator (ship possessor) and assumes the role of shipowner (in the sense of "ship operator") for the duration of the charter. This means the bareboat charterer is responsible for crewing, maintenance, and all operational matters, and effectively acts as the shipowner in relation to third parties. By contrast, when the registered shipowner directly operates the vessel by appointing the master and crew, he is both the legal ship owner and the ship possessor (i.e., the operator or managing owner).

In contrast, under a time charter, the registered owner or bareboat charterer (as disponent owner) charters out the vessel to the time charterer, who takes over commercial operation and pays for voyage expenses, including port disbursements and fuel costs. In this arrangement, the registered shipowner or bareboat charterer (as disponent owner) retains technical management and bears the daily operational costs of the vessel. Legal possession of the vessel does not transfer to the time charterer, who does not become the ship possessor but only gains control over the vessel's employment.

The end charterer – typically the cargo interest – pays the freight and is responsible for arranging berthing and cargo handling at the loading and discharging ports.

Where a voyage charter is concluded over a vessel that is already subject to preceding bareboat and/or time charter agreements, a complex legal question arises as to who bears responsibility for the proper performance of the voyage charter and for the cargo under the bill of lading. In a chain of charter parties, the party liable under the voyage charter may not necessarily be the same party liable under the bill of lading – an issue examined separately in a later section of this article.

The contractual nature of voyage charters places them at the core of **tramp shipping**, where vessels operate privately and independently, without fixed schedules. A critical feature of such agreements is the **Free In and Out** freight term, which allocates loading and unloading responsibilities and costs to the charterer, while the shipowner remains liable for the safe stowage of cargo.

From a legal standpoint, voyage charters are shaped by key distinctions between **port**, **berth**, and **dock charterparties**, each defining the moment of "arrival" differently—a factor that directly affects the commencement of laytime and the liability for demurrage. Case law such as *The Aello*, *Leonis v. Rank*, and *The Delian Spirit* illustrates the nuanced judicial interpretation of these distinctions.

Moreover, the structure of **charter chains** adds complexity to the legal obligations between parties, especially when different forms of charters (bareboat, time, or voyage) are layered. Finally, the paper situates the voyage charter within a historical and comparative framework, acknowledging its deep roots in European commercial traditions and its enduring significance in contemporary maritime logistics and legal practice.

2. Description of the Voyage Charter under English Private Maritime Law

Definition by Plomaritou and Papadopoulos (2018, pp. 323–324):

A voyage charter is a contract under which a named vessel is hired for a single voyage between specified ports. The owner retains operational control and bears voyage expenses, while the charterer pays freight per ton of cargo and covers cargo-related costs.[4]

Voyage charters are used for the transport of goods between two or more ports. They are also used for the transport of large quantities of goods for one shipper, with one or more ships of one carrier, within a long period – the so-called **Contract of Affreightment** (Poel, 2023) [5] and **Volume Contract** (Law Insider, 2023). [6] In voyage charters, the cargo on board the ship usually belongs to one charterer (shipper), but it is also common practice, with the consent of the main shipper, to transport other incidental cargo (**part cargo**) to a second shipper, if there is free space on board the ship. In voyage charters, the shipowner owns and operates the ship (technically and commercially). A voyage charter carrier may be the actual shipowner or a bareboat charterer or time charterer, if a corresponding charter for the ship has been concluded. A voyage charter carrier may also be a voyage charterer under a previous voyage charter for the same cargo (in the case of a chain of charters). The technical operation of the ship is carried out by the ship's crew and technical personnel

on shore, who are appointed, directed and controlled by the shipowner (shipowner or bareboat charterer). The commercial operation of the ship is carried out by the relevant commercial department (**chartering department**) of the carrier who concluded the contract of carriage (shipowner or bareboat charterer or time charterer). These charters are used in the tramp shipping organization, in which the carrier operates the merchant ship for its own account as a **private carrier**, also called **contract carrier**. The carrier carries out its own commercial activity, consisting in the transportation of foreign goods against an agreed freight. In these contracts, the carrier is usually not responsible for the loading and unloading of the goods, i.e. the cargo is transported on net terms (**Free In Out Terms**). The obligation and costs of loading and unloading the goods are at the expense of the charterer (shipper) of the ship, but the responsibility for the correct loading remains with the shipowner (who is represented by the ship's captain). Fixed costs (**daily running costs** and **capital costs**) of the ship are at the expense of the shipowner (shipowner or bareboat charterer), the variable costs (**voyage expenses**) of the ship are for the account of the carrier as per the voyage charter (the shipowner or bareboat charterer or time charterer). The charterer (shipper) pays the shipowner freight and is usually obliged to arrange and pay for the transshipment activities related to the cargo. In a chain of charters, the ship may have previously been given out on Bareboat - Charter and / or Time - Charter. In these cases, the shipper's obligations under the voyage charter are preserved, but in relation to the carrier under the voyage charter, his actual obligations apply and in accordance with his contractual obligations under the previous charter in the chain of charters. From the point of view of theory and practice, there may be two consecutive voyage charters in the chain of charters. In this situation, the obligations of the charterers under the successive voyage charters remain unchanged and in accordance with what was agreed upon under them.

2.1. Description of vessel

According to Plomaritou and Papadopoulos (2018, p. 324):

"In most cases a specific ship is nominated. Thus, the vessel's name, IMO identification number and call sign, year of build, nationality, deadweight, gross and net tonnage and sometimes speed are stated in the charter party."

"Both the owners and the charterers must, as far as possible, try to specify all those details about the cargo and the vessel that are necessary for economic calculation and practical planning of the loading, carrying, and discharging of a cargo." [4]

2.2. Description of the Voyage

(Plomaritou and Papadopoulos, 2018, pp 330-331) explain that the voyage description in a charterparty may involve flexible or fixed nomination of ports and berths. When not predetermined, charterers are expected to nominate ports within a reasonable timeframe to prevent delay or deviation. To minimize steaming time, the concept of "geographical rotation" is frequently included (pp. 325–326). [4]

2.3. Description of the Cargo:

(Plomaritou & Papadopoulos, 2018). “*The description of the cargo is important for several reasons. Owners who, during the negotiations and in the fixture, accepted a certain cargo are also obliged to carry out the transportation of this cargo. This means that the owners must get all necessary details of the cargo [...] to find out whether the cargo is suitable for the vessel and estimate the costs [...].*”[4]

2.4. Freight determination

(Plomaritou & Papadopoulos, 2018, pp. 332–333). The freight can be fixed in several different ways. One way is to base it on the cargo quantity [...] Another way is to fix the freight at a certain amount independent of the cargo quantity [...]. The principal rule is that the freight is earned when the owners have fulfilled their obligation to carry the cargo and are ready to deliver it to the receiver [...] if the owners cannot deliver the cargo, they are not entitled to freight. [4]

2.5. Formation of Binding Agreements

(Cooke et al. 2014, 1.3–1.4) emphasize that under English law, a voyage charterparty does not need to follow any particular form or be formally signed. What matters is that “the parties should have reached a firm agreement upon all essential terms.” The agreement may arise through emails, oral communication, or even conduct, provided the intention to contract is clear. This contractual flexibility allows voyage charters to be well-suited to inland tramp shipping, where informal but operative agreements are often necessary due to practical navigation and scheduling constraints. [1]

2.6. Intention to Create Legal Relations

(Cooke et al., 2014, para 1.12-1.15) underline the foundational principle in English law that no contract is formed unless both parties intend to be legally bound. The mutual intention must be outwardly manifested, not merely privately held:

(Cooke et al., 2014). “Since a mutual intention to contract is required, it is necessary that both parties should intend to be contractually bound. However, the private intentions of either party are irrelevant, except insofar as they were, or should have been, known to the other. As Lord Denning said in *Storer v. Manchester C.C.*: ‘In contracts you do not investigate the actual intent in a man’s mind. You look at what he said and did. A contract is formed when there is, to all outward appearances, a contract. A man cannot get out of a contract by saying ‘I did not intend to contract’ if by his words he has done so.’”

This position is particularly relevant in the context of charterparty negotiations, where parties often proceed based on recap messages, and formal execution may follow later without affecting the contract’s binding nature—unless explicitly stated otherwise. [1]

2.7. Temporary Agreements (Subjects)

(Cooke et al., 2014, para 1.16–1.26). In charterparty negotiations, the use of provisional clauses known as “**subjects**” serves to suspend or condition the parties’ contractual obligations until certain conditions are fulfilled. These **temporary agreements** are not intended to be legally binding unless and until the rele-

vant subject is lifted. Their legal effect has been clarified in numerous cases, depending on their wording, context, and subsequent conduct of the parties.

Common expressions include:

- **"Subject to contract"** – This typically means that no binding agreement exists until a formal contract is signed. In *A-G of Hong Kong v. Humphreys Estate (1987)*, the Privy Council held that such language indicated a clear intention not to be bound prior to contract execution.

- **"Subject to details"** – This expression, often inserted after agreement on main terms, indicates that no contract is formed until all remaining details are agreed. In *The Junior K* [1988] 2 Lloyd’s Rep 583, Steyn J. confirmed that even where major terms were settled, the inclusion of this subject meant that no binding charterparty had been concluded.

- **"Subject to stem"** – This clause conditions the charter on cargo availability during the intended loading period. In *Kokusai Kisen v. Johnson (1921)* 8 Ll L Rep 124, the court concluded that this phrase rendered the arrangement inoperative unless the cargo was confirmed.

- **"Subject to survey"** – Here, the agreement is conditional upon a satisfactory survey of the vessel or cargo. In *The Merak* [1965] 1 Lloyd’s Rep 464, although the inspection was a formal step, the Sale form and the parties’ conduct led the court to conclude that a binding contract existed.

- **"Subject to board approval", "subject to review", or "subject to trial voyage"** – These clauses suspend effectiveness until a third party (often the charterer’s head office or technical team) gives approval. As seen in *The John S. Darbyshire* [1977] 2 Lloyd’s Rep 457, trial voyage success was a condition precedent, and failure to satisfy it meant no contract was in place.

Some phrases, such as “**subject to logical amendments**”, have a less decisive legal effect. In *The CPC Gallia* [1994] 2 Lloyd’s Rep 468, the court held that this wording did not create a binding agreement, as parties anticipated further negotiation on standard form options.

Overall, the legal significance of **subjects** depends on

- The natural meaning of the expression.
- The context and standard industry usage.
- The conduct of the parties after initial agreement.

As a general rule, unless the subject is clearly lifted or waived, no binding agreement is formed. The courts take a strict approach to such wording, especially in chartering, where even slight variations in expression may shift the legal effect. [1]

3. Types of shipping charters depending on when the ship is considered to have arrived:

• Port Charter Party

According to Davies (2006), the concept of “arriving ship” in the context of port charterparties involves the interpretation of the concepts of “port” and “trading area” to determine the moment when the ship has reached its final destination. This is essential for wait-

ing time and demurrage . Key legal cases such as *Leonis v. Rank* , *The Aello* and *The Delian Spirit* examines how courts define the boundaries of ports and their trading zones, which influences when a ship is considered to have arrived and when the waiting time begins (Davies, 2006).

- **Berth Charter Party**

(Davies, 2006, pp. 47–52) is a contract under which the vessel must reach a specific, predetermined or nominated berth for loading or unloading. In such contracts, the laytime **begins to run only after the physical arrival of the vessel at the berth itself**, if there is operational readiness and a notice of readiness has been given. **of readiness**). The point here is that arrival in the port area alone is not enough - actual arrival at the quay is required. If the quay is temporarily occupied or unavailable, the ship must wait, and the risk of this delay is usually borne by the carrier, unless otherwise stipulated in the contract.

- **Dock Charter Party** (used without translation)

(Davies, 2006, pp. 54-55). Under a dock charter party, the ship is deemed to have arrived when it enters the dock, without the need to reach the specific berth for loading or unloading. Lord Diplock in *Oldendorff* confirmed that "entering the dock and mooring is all that is necessary to reach the agreed place." [7]

4. Shipowners' Responsibility in Voyage Chartering

(Cooke et al., 2014, p. 228). Owners are to be responsible for loss of or damage to the goods or for delay in delivery of the goods only in case the loss, damage or delay has been caused by the improper or negligent stowage of the goods (unless stowage performed by Shippers/Charterers or their Stevedores or Servants) or by personal want of due diligence on the part of the Owners or their Manager to make the vessel in all respects seaworthy and to secure that she is properly manned, equipped and supplied or by the personal act or default of the Owners or their Manager. [1]

4.1. Determining the Carrier as stated in the Bill of Lading and endorsing the Bill of Lading.

(Dimitrakiev, Koritarov, & Velinov, 2025, pp. 46-52). The identification of the carrier under the bill of lading is a pivotal aspect of maritime law, as it fundamentally determines accountability for the cargo being transported. [...] Bills of lading that are signed by the ship's master and do not have a clearly indicated carrier's name are generally considered to be bills of lading issued by the shipowner. In accordance with common practice, the carrier's name should be filled in the specified blank area located in the upper right corner of the second page of the bill of lading. If this section is not completed, it is assumed that the shipowner serves as the carrier.[8]

5. Shipowners' and Charterers' obligations

The parties are subject to a series of obligations when they utilize voyage charter agreements. In some cases, the requirements of these contracts are negotiated through intermediaries who act on behalf of one of the parties (shipowner or charterer). Brokers connect

shipowners with companies that require the transportation of products, and freight brokers typically participate.

5.1. Shipowners' obligations

Providing a seaworthy vessel on the specified date, ensuring that it is in a condition that is suitable for navigation and appropriate for the type of cargo to be transported. This entails verifying that the vessel is suitable for the specific cargo and that all requisite certifications and documents are in order. The vessel may be inspected by charterers or their designees at any point during the term to confirm that it satisfies the terms of the charter contract. The owner's prior sanction is required for such inspections, and it shall not be withheld without reasonable cause. Inspections should be conducted without obstructing the vessel's safe and efficient operation.

The cargo must be delivered in a satisfactory condition by the shipowner at the conclusion of the voyage. They are accountable for the cargo while it is on the vessel.

The selection of the most suitable nautical route.

Employing and compensating the personnel, as well as incurring all substantial expenses associated with the expedition.

Additionally, the shipowner is required to maintain sufficient insurance coverage for liability, crew, and any other necessary components to mitigate potential risks during the charter period.

5.2. Charterer's obligations

Pay the freight charges and any other associated expenses in accordance with the charter contract's terms. It is imperative to observe contractual obligations and avoid disputes by making timely payments.

Guaranteeing that the cargo is prepared for loading at the designated time and location. This entails the coordination with the shipowner and port authorities to expedite cargo operations and the provision of all requisite documentation.

As agreed, upon, the expenses associated with loading and unloading operations or services.

Arrange for any supplementary insurance that is necessary for the cargo, in addition to the coverage provided by the shipowner's policy, to guarantee comprehensive protection against potential hazards during the voyage.

Ensure that all customs and port regulations are adhered to at the loading and discharge terminals, if applicable. This encompasses the acquisition of any required permits or certifications to prevent legal complications or delays.

6. Other perspectives on Voyage Charter

(Vialard, 1997, p. 331). "The freight charter is the oldest charter known to French Commercial Code of 1807". The voyage charter is a mutual and reciprocal obligation. One party promises to carry a certain quantity of cargo from point A to point B, while the other party promises to deliver the goods to the ship and pay the freight. In a voyage charter, the shipper chartered the ship for a certain voyage regardless of its duration, in other words, "**time runs against the shipowner**". [9]

Another characteristic of the contract concerns the important role played by the cargo, because the subject

of the contract is detailed, well described and individualized. This consideration of the cargo is of specific importance for voyage chartering. The last characteristic element of the voyage charter is the fact that the contract is based on the idea of the rotational sign of speed for the fulfillment of the obligations of the contracting parties. Although the carrier assumes several obligations by providing the ship described in the contract at the agreed place and time for the agreed voyage, voyage chartering also includes the extended participation of the charterer. The speed of the fulfillment of the contract depends not only on one of the parties, but on both. The speed of the contract depends very much on the charterer. For the carrier to fulfill its obligations, it must receive the cargo from the charterer as early as possible. The voyage contract for the carriage of goods by sea and inland waterways is one of the two types of contracts used in water transport.

7. Application of Voyage Charter: (Cooke et al., 2014, p. 123). Voyage charters are used in tramp shipping. They are negotiated and signed between the carrier and the charterer, after which the contractual relationship is deemed to have arisen, and accordingly their performance begins. [1]

(Heisenberg Shipping, 2025). A voyage charter is the predominant arrangement in the dry bulk shipping sector. In essence, it is a contract in which a shipowner leases their vessel to transport goods between certain ports. In contrast to other charter parties, a voyage charter pertains only to a singular journey of the vessel. This is the reason marine sector stakeholders refer to it as "voyage chartering." The agreement is termed a charter party, and the conditions are established on a trip basis. The shipowner provides the vessel to a charterer at a designated loading port on a predetermined date (see to "Laycan" and "Cancelling date"). The shipowner bears all expenses. This includes gasoline, port and canal fees, and stevedoring if required. It includes hold cleaning, dunnage, if necessary, commissions, agency fees, freight taxes, and insurance. [10]

(Marlinblue, n.d.). A voyage charter agreement is a particular type of maritime contract in which the shipowner offers the charterer a single voyage on a vessel. Under a voyage charter agreement, there are two primary options:

1. Full vessel charter: In this situation, the charterer is granted exclusive use of the entire vessel, which is then utilized for a specific voyage, utilizing all available cargo space. This may be utilized for:

A single voyage is required to transport a full cargo from one port to another. The vessel is chartered to transport cargo to a destination and then return with additional cargo in round-trip voyages.

Numerous journeys for a sequence of predetermined excursions within a specified time frame.

Voyages that involve multiple ports, where the charterer is permitted to load and discharge cargo at distinct harbors in accordance with the terms of the contract.

2. Partial vessel charter (part cargo): In a partial charter, the charterer reserves only a portion of the vessel's cargo space. When the charterer does not require

the vessel's full capacity, this alternative is appropriate. It is optimal for:

Specific machinery, vehicles, or other goods that require independent transportation without the need to consolidate full load are considered smaller shipments that do not occupy the full cargo space. [11]

7.1. Common cargo types

The voyage charter agreement is adaptable and can be employed to convey a variety of cargo over a specific voyage. The primary categories of cargo that are conveyed under this agreement are as follows:

Bulk products include grains, coal, ores, and minerals. These commodities are frequently conveyed in substantial quantities and are particularly well-suited for voyage charters due to their weight and volume.

Crude oil, refined petroleum products, and compounds comprise liquid cargo. These cargos frequently necessitate specialized vessels, such as tankers, that are chartered for specific voyages between designated ports.

Breakbulk cargo includes vehicles, construction materials, and apparatus. These are frequently conveyed on multipurpose vessels, where the cargo dimensions and specific handling requirements are considered to optimize space utilization.

7.2. Common routes

The demand in specific regions and the type of cargo being conveyed determine the most common routes for voyage charters.

For instance, voyage charters are frequently implemented in the context of short-sea transportation within Europe. These routes frequently involve the transportation of a variety of bulk products between ports in the Baltic, North Sea, and Mediterranean regions. Voyage charters are advantageous for these shorter itineraries, as they enable shippers to utilize a vessel for a single, well-defined journey without committing to long-term contracts. This adaptability is essential for accommodating fluctuating cargo volumes and market conditions, rendering it an optimal option for shortsea operations.

Voyage charters are frequently employed in the Atlantic trade to transport crude oil from West Africa to significant refining centers in the United States and Europe. Oil companies can capitalize on fluctuations in oil prices and demand by securing vessels on a per-trip basis through the voyage charter party agreement. In the same vein, voyage charter agreements are more advantageous for Australia's export of bulk commodities, such as coal and iron ore, to China and Japan in the Pacific region. This type of contract allows exporters to optimize their shipping requirements by coordinating production schedules and seasonal demand based on specific cargo volumes and shipment scheduling.

Conclusion

The voyage charter remains a central contractual instrument in private maritime law, particularly under English legal tradition, due to its adaptability to the needs of bulk cargo transport in the tramp shipping sector. Its legal and financial characteristics, most notably the clear allocation of responsibilities, the Free In and Out terms, and the freight structures—make it suitable for commercial transactions involving individual or

multiple voyages. The complexity increases when voyage charters are embedded within a chain of charterparties, raising issues of liability and contractual performance. Nevertheless, the voyage charter retains a high degree of legal clarity and commercial relevance. Its enduring application in modern maritime logistics confirms its importance as a legally distinct and economically efficient mode of carriage, especially when analyzed considering English case law and contractual doctrine.

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